

A Learning Pathway for Enhancing Adult's Green Awareness and Competence on Job Opportunities and Wellbeing

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Abstract

Responding to climate change and environmental challenges demands more than political commitments, it requires equipping citizens with the competences to adapt, participate, and thrive. Europe's labour market is being reshaped by the green transition, yet its rapid pace risks leaving many adults behind. While demand for sustainability-driven skills is accelerating, emerging skilled adults often remain under-prepared, underrepresented, and vulnerable to the pressures of a changing work environment, with direct consequences for their wellbeing. The Erasmus+ project Green4ADU: a cooperation across Germany, Italy, Greece, Spain, and the Netherlands - addresses this skills gap by embedding green competences into adult education. The project adopts a pragmatic, research-based approach: developing an open-access learning pathway that combines digital modules with hands-on practice. Professor Cha-Hsuan Liu, as the Research Lead in the Netherlands, and EU partners co-design curricula with learners and educators to ensure both scientific rigour and relevance. Peer review, community-based workshops, and iterative feedback loops reinforce the programme's quality and inclusivity.

As of summer 2025, a six-module online course available in six languages has been developed and will be trialled in autumn. Its themes, identified through surveys and focus groups across the partnership countries, range from climate literacy and circular economy to urban gardening and nature-based wellbeing. Complementary local workshops further ground the learning in context and foster inclusive participation. By 2026, Green4ADU will deliver the scalable e-learning modules, a replicable educator toolkit, and evidence-based policy recommendations to support the integration of green competences into adult education systems in a global scale. Green competences for emerging skilled adults is critical for both employability and social inclusion. Dr Liu uses the experience gained from the EU Green4ADU project further highlights the key considerations for designing education that equips emerging skilled adults not only with employable skills, but also with resilience, agency, and the capacity to contribute meaningfully to green transition.

Keywords: *climate change, green competences, green transition, job opportunities and wellbeing*